

Introduction

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Description

This document is an observational assessment as well as being tool. The document will reflect a personal perspective in certain observations it is "human" in assessment. This document is not declaring perfection in any shape or form. This document is a framework not an absolute. This document is built for the purpose of education, inflection, reflection and curiousness. To provoke thought and conversation. We cannot live through each and every persons eyes and ears. We can however communicate and share our observations to one another.

If you are interested in a modest average opinion and outlook on various topics. If you are searching. If your curiosity gets the better of you. Possibly any such reason. However you discovered this framework its for you to shape into whatever suits you best. Enjoy.

Thank you for reading, I appreciate you taking your time.

Sincerely;

Victor Lyman

Development

We are born.

There are many factors at play as to how. You may look towards the many ways in a biblical, scientific or other way. The truth though it may not be appreciated or agreed upon is still truth. Clear honest truth, though it may disrupt your outlook cannot be refuted and you may lie to yourself about the what, where, when, why and how of it all. You still cannot refute your own existence or presence. The human equation 1(M) Male+1(F) Female=1 or more offspring, Science and technology make other ways possible but the seed and the egg are still a requirement to some extent.

You exist for a reason, for a purpose. Don't lie to yourself you only close doors.

We are given consciousnesses.

No longer blind to all our senses. The world is ours to discover. Instincts, senses, emotions and much more start to arise. This is the point of ones life where external factors begin to effect internal networks greater. When complexity of learning is of interaction and approach. When you are most afflicted by rapid changes in all personal ways. These years are the most crucial for development. Don't deprive this developmental phase unless you desire a dependency in the future. Mannerisms, Forethought, Lessons in moderation, self control, social and common decency along with so much more are in need of delicate care for independent growth. In a world that adapts externally in a rigorous manor sometimes explosive manor it becomes ever more difficult to balance said growth.

We have a tendency to overwhelm and be overwhelmed. This is a cause of societal influence and self moderation. Don't continually clash with nature and nurture, observe.

We are taught.

Communication different shapes and forms of. The opposite is less taught more practiced observation. We put greater value in how well we communicate and less how we observe. This causes an imbalance and hysterically enough a miss of communication. You pose an external or internal observation with the expectancy that the one whom you posed knows of your observation. The blind lead the blind. If you expect direct the observation with explanation and clarity an understanding or observation can be made. Possibly another observation. Judgment, ridicule and other pessimistic approaches to life conflict with the want to observe or communicate an observation. So here is a way to look at this problem, why object yourself to internal berating when it's simply a view point as long you remain translucent and open to contradictions your point can be made. If emotion gets in the way of thought it's your own lack of control and that is all to human. If thought is in your head you are the only one able to share it not others unless communicated. Pessimism is a necessity for balance and growth same as optimism. Too much of a good thing and all. Do you want sameness in a varying shade of gray. No. We are not creatures of sameness. It's learning how to approach the internal and external conflicts that may arise productively.

We cannot avoid miss communication. We can however monitor ourselves in how we respond. Don't let the river force you into the rapids, navigate the river with carefully thought out intent.

We inherit a world of wonder.

Experience

Your experience in life

This is a product of your inheritance, influences, society, family and much more. All these factor into your experience and perspective crafting a different model of yourself which changes by the fraction of a millisecond. You are not the same person that you were seconds ago and that is profound, yet not deniable. An ever changing rhythm a cadence to be danced the waltz of personality if you will. Entertaining though it may seem it doesn't diminish the value in fact it creates a weight an orchestra or a beautiful symphony that sustains your presence of being. You are harmonized and in tune with everything around you whether you see it or not.

Walk within yourself, don't run. Learn all the boundaries of your mind and find balance with clarity without losing yourself.

Others experience.

Be mindful and respectful, this is unknown territory. You nor I or anyone for that matter knows this opinion completely. The Internal and external limitations are unknown waters to be carefully swam. Others are just as complex ones self, they vary similar to how you vary. Yet are completely different. Do not fool yourself, others are just as experienced as you only in other aspects of life. Common decency, manners, and insights are all different and that is what makes them fascinating. Don't push or pull, add emotion or only take at face value, don't put up unnecessary walls or opinions. Closing doors and opening up ones self to uncertainty. This uncertainty is what thins the scale of trust in the vast society which we live.

Walk with ease, and respect for ones self as well others. The key is in keeping mask on intent and emotion hiding true opinion. Stick to the facts and measuring with care.

Societal experience.

As a whole we are an experiment in consciousness. Experience is the fuel to this consciousness. This agreement with reality.

What is known for certain is we should value experience.

Stress

Let's look at and into stress, shall we.

Stress in all its forms. Self induced stress. Brought on by perceptions and emotions. Whether consciously or unconsciously caused, not of fault or will but belonging and belief. Instinctive response adapted and evolved with the species never consistent with each person. Unique to one's self. The struggle within. A necessary force.

General stress outward pressure and perception. A constant form of unmanaged feeling and thought. Physically and mentally draining but also allows for growth with caution. Imposed stress a Social weight, indoctrination and influence mashing into control and management of force upon others. Vile but not always, if used for good reason can teach respect, restraint and responsibility along with other great and useful skills when used with care.

Stress is part of life we give it many names and impose cruel labels which set as a distinction and reminder of difference in ability, tool set, and more. While saying it's for good reason in truth it is the dark side of humanity. We seek difference in every aspect IE. "it's always something". The question is when it comes to an actual stressors like mental illness or disability. Can you and do you have a right to impose your thoughts upon them. Do you have a clear reason, tool, or way to help them. Make sure it's not because they are different from you and that is your justification, that is flawed logic. Help those in need not with intention or provocation imposing righteous judgment but with humility and understanding. There is a time and place for everything and knowing when to stop and start is crucial.

Stress is many things but evil it is not. Therefore stress is not an excuse the cause of stress is. You can't push a syringe into your arm if it doesn't have a needle. You made the bed you lay in. For better or worse and it's not always your fault for giving into stress, it is yours if you take away choice and abandon yourself. The excuse becomes a justification for the self. You may have your choices taken from you and that is a cruel yet not uncommon truth but if given a chance don't make excuses.

I'll phrase in another outlook.

A Pretend Scenario -

I am born with the itch. My mother gave this to me. My father abuses it as well, this itch. This downpour, This cloudiness. I can't see past my present I have little knowledge of life and most everything within it, I don't care, I itch and tell myself That I hope it ends tomorrow all of it but don't know the unknown only this itch. And my world is small. This is not of my fault but know not how to tell myself only blame everything and crave the itch. This is normal this is my constant conditioning, my inherent nature, I know not how to break the mold for futures to come.

This context is a cruel yet honest look into a life that has had choice taken and now takes.

Let us break down stress.

Stress= factors

Stress causes adaptation

Stress causes caution

Stress creates cause

Stress is simply a word to communicate underlying factors at play that cause disruption in the self even if unknown. There is always a stressor at play.

Let's look deeper and ask the question what is stress to you, do you see the need and the potential while also seeing the harshness and uncertainty. Can you find middle ground and build a tool out of different stressors to manage stress at different levels. Can you see harmony, can you feel the good, the motivating. The push not the pull. You can look upon light and see darkness depending on how you use stress in consciousness or unconsciousness. It's blurs your perception and person in all aspects whether you wish it to or not it simply will. It's coming to terms with stress and finding ways to make it beneficial for yourself and or others.

So is stress not beautiful and meaningful. Stress is a mental framing. A harsh but beautiful lesson. Stress= truth. And there is a beauty in truth and clarity but only if you want it to be.

I will continue to build upon this but for now may this become a useful tool or conversation piece. You may use this as you see fit.

Observation

The beauty of life

In womb our cells expand till our bodies are able to sustain us, A process of months inside our mother. During this period the mother is our world. Once birth takes place development and indoctrination into society begins. This is where thoughts, opinions and actions of others affect our perspective and cause us to adapt to the situation we are in. Internally and externally. This then establishes our place in society, our worth if you will. This is where silly titles are made. We made up language, clothing, morals, ethics, and society. To establish dominance in the beginning, be it dominance over climate or one another. I.e one monkey telling another monkey what to do, it doesn't make any sense. Unless it benefits both parties or a singular for various reasons. You always have motives in every action you make whether or not your aware of it.

Take mine for example in writing this, to voice my observations thus far in life. It's simply time. If the words are a string in my mind it's ignorant of me to believe anyone knows exactly what I've observed if I don't voice it. Professionally and productively to a better degree, perfection I'm not. I'm an average person no better than the poor or rich. I see no difference, except in societal station. I look beyond all societal concepts and constructs to value the worth of some one. I look at intent and behavior. A more basic approach to viewing a person. Instead of guessing internal or external predictions. I look at capability. I understand governance and it's importance especially when faced with uncertainty. I simply refuse to lie to myself that society or governance, and life for that matter are anything more than it's chalked up to be. You are a human being, there are others similar to yourself. So I understand the need for leadership, guidance, governance. Uncertainty and Survival. It makes life more predictable, as well gives a solid structure net. We draw lines and look for difference it's within human nature, you simply need to understand this. As long as lines aren't crossed without justification and clarity as long as difference in all shapes and forms is looked at professionally and productively we can reach understanding. Not agreement, understanding. Knowledge is useful in aspects of life but must be balanced with understanding or conflict arises.

I am against no one, nor do I care. Opinion and judgments are made. It's what you choose to do with it. When I say I don't care it has to do with moderation and experience. I don't care as in I don't have any warranted opinion in the matter so there for I should not care to pry or spew needless info. Holding tongue. Speaking when spoken too, Listening and observing before action. If I don't pose a probable and conscious opinion in a matter it's not of mine to speak unless formulated to my distinct outlook or observations thus far. I look at the bigger picture for better or worse. That doesn't excuse the small things in life or make light of them. That said it is in how you perceive. Your small thing could very well be big picture to someone which is the beauty of creating dialog. I may overlook or misjudge, that's okay I'm human. I am of low education and below average in memory and iq. This alone doesn't disqualify my observations nor should it yours.

We may hold our tongue on opinions to spare a person or person(s) but in doing so we give them the rod brought on by an inability an inadequacy to follow through with truth. This prevents growth and understanding of ones self. Emotion stand points and dis regulation in thought is of something we have in common our emotions get in the way of logic but adds to perception and inheritance. One without the other, logic without emotion is fact but not reality.

